

EXPLORING AMERICAN REALISM: A JOURNEY THROUGH THE 19TH CENTURY LITERARY LANDSCAPE

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Abstract. This article delves into the captivating artistic and literary movement known as American Realism, which emerged in the late 19th century and provided a profound reflection of American society during a period of significant transformation. It explores the key features of American Realism, highlighting its commitment to portraying everyday life with unvarnished honesty and its focus on ordinary people. The article also discusses notable figures of this movement, including Mark Twain, Henry James, F. Scott Fitzgerald, Ernest Hemingway, and Toni Morrison, who contributed unique perspectives to the genre. American Realism's roots in the post-Civil War era of rapid industrialization and social change are examined, emphasizing how this period provided a fertile ground for authors to address social issues and depict the complexities of American life.

Key words: American Realism, artistic movement, literary movement, late 19th century, transformation, everyday life, unvarnished honesty, ordinary people.

American Realism is a captivating artistic and literary movement that emerged in the late 19th century, offering a profound reflection of the evolving American society during a time of great transformation. Characterized by its emphasis on depicting everyday life with unvarnished honesty and a focus on the ordinary, this movement provided a stark departure from the romanticized ideals of previous eras. Through this introduction, we will embark on a journey to explore the key features,

notable figures, and enduring impact of American Realism on both the arts and the broader cultural landscape.

American Realism and representatives

Realism in American Books goes back to the 19th century, 1860-1900. In American books, realism is described as a term that includes the period from the time of the Civil Warfare to the 20th century-an period where the realism of Twain and Wayne was highly praised. Realism in America was therefore a 20th century idea in literature by which reflections of the time were portrayed. A time in which creators like Mark Twain, Henry James, F. Scott Fitzgerald, Ernest Hemmingway, Toni Morrison and others wrote books that was dedicated to accurate explanation and a report of the way the Americans lived in different situations during that era. After the Civil War, there is a fast expansion throughout the market and population in the United States. This rapid development in the rates of industrialization, urbanization, an escalating human population base because of this of immigration, standard literacy, public equality and a growth in the affluence of the middle-class inhabitants presented a wealthy base for writers and visitors who experienced the urge to understand these rapid changes in the American civilization.

In determining the realism in the literary background of America, we make reference to that period which range from 1865 to 1914, which has been commonly referred to as the Age of Realism in the American literary record. Therefore, in defining Realism as a literary movement, it ought to be specifically situated in history and not artistically labeled to flee being dated. Hence, Realism being regarded as a literary movement, it should doubtless be limited to the age from the past due 1840s to the middle 1860s. Therefore that the idea of focus regarding literal realism of the content should be devoted to the ordinary, every day lives of the lower-class preferably. The American realist freelance writers went ahead to build their plots and characters around the normal, daily lives that folks led. Furthermore, their fictional works included local dialects and wide-ranging interactions that attached

well with the community. Consequently, readers were ideally drawn to the realistic writers because they could see their own challenges on the net. The American public got advanced socially, economically and politically and they also tended to like writers who plainly defined the difficulties of each day life for individuals as opposed to the slow-moving paced writings and symbolism of the intimate writers, which the public possessed come to develop distaste for. The US citizens had transformed to a new years, and realism was the only theory that evidently depicted the problem as it certainly was throughout that age.

Mark uses local colorism as a style through which he presents life through representing the personas in his book as locals from a particular region. The way they did things in a local manner, the clothes that they used and even how they talked explained their lifestyle in a profound way. Make Twain unlike Adam Henry composed about people in the lower-class. Being the type of life he previously lived, he recognized this class of people better as observed in his novels. Through use of local colorism, Tag was able to illustrate and shed light on issues in the modern society.

The Gilded age group, as Mark Twain commonly identifies as the time of American realism, was a time of materialism and politics corruption in the United States. These elements produced ideas which some important works of fiction on politics and social criticism were predicated on. The novel «Gilded Age» (1873), that was authored by Symbol Twain and Charles Dudley Warner, presents a specific depiction of Washington D. C. The field describes fraudulent politicians and insatiable industrialists. The novels of this years characterize the beginning of a fresh twist in the American books, with the book acting as a car of communal grievances. In an attempt to spell it out a modern-day view of how things were in reality; writing was used to portray the way the culture of the folks and the scenic prospect of NEW YORK had altered in this time. During this period of your time, the freelance writers, journalists, music artists and painters experienced made a significant contribution to

the idea of realism in the American setting; that they had actually come old. This was actually a new kind of era freelance writers, journalists and painters who through their writing and artwork were worried about representing the most common and common aspects of life in an easy and unemotional manner, that was assumed to portray life as it actually was.

Their strategy of treating things that portray a careful depiction of daily life, more so by the low and middle classes was partly influenced by the new city life of an people who have been more urban as opposed to leading a rural life and partly by the works of elderly American writers. These North american realists did think that humanity's personal preferences and freedom of preference were constrained by the supremacy of outside the house forces, which influence our means of thinking and consequently our action and personality. This is a new get older and it possessed come with a new style and procedure of writing and presenting other works of art. (Patterson)

Henry James and Draw Twain are some of the renowned freelance writers in this time and mutually they achieved to draw out the indigenous style in the genuine information of the land and interpersonal activities utilizing the colloquial speech style. By using this approach they managed to survey and use the imaginary potential of the interior life of folks living at the time. However, the three authors differed in their belief of what they referred to as the truth in reality. For instance, Symbol and William gave more emphasis to the overall life of the People in america, while Henry offered more attention to the sub conscious components of a person. Henry was of the judgment that literary music artists should use words to explore the deepest extents of the mental and ethical nature of folks in addition to analyzing the exterior of interpersonal life in certain circumstances. This made him a realist of both the internal and outer life, while Mark and William were simply realists of the surface life.

The contribution of these five authors; Mark Twain, Henry Wayne, F. Scott Fitzgerald, Ernest Hemmingway, Toni Morrison to the American realism through Literature may very well be fitting in the genuine period in the American books in this context. Samuel Clemens, commonly known by his family pet name Mark Twain is famous for how he represented realism in his writing (1835-1910). His well-known literary works are Tom Sawyer plus the Travels of Huckleberry Finn. In his book, The Ventures of Huckleberry Finn, his most prominent accounts of realism, he released a character Huckleberry Finn who's a mistreated and neglected thirteen yrs. Old boy, whose father is a cruel drunk. From Finn's view point, we reach start to see the world as he attempts to make sense of the communal world around him. Within the story, Tag portrays various societal formalities by representing the dual standards of the civilized American culture atlanta divorce attorneys day life.

Mark Twain's style, that was based on a dynamic, useful and slang American language, offered to the American authors and viewers an admiration of the speech that symbolized a new form of American fiction. Despite Symbol from the interiors of the country, he was actually among the most crucial authors who managed to capture this unique colloquial vocabulary and the aspect of iconoclasm of the People in the usa in his writing. However in his impression, realism was not just a literary skill: It had been a means of revealing the reality and abandoning old-fashioned basic principle of life. Like other natural writers at that time, Mark Twain symbolizes life in a practical way. His mode of writing was amusing, descriptive and one that integrated the colloquial terms of People in america with both slang and iconoclasm. Tag Twain is regarded as a major article writer in the practical period. Through his literature, Tag created the world's view of the United States. From how he managed to incorporate the American people's laughter and serious writing, he produced a very superb form of books than the earlier novelists had ever before done.

Throughout his writing job, Mark Twain used the approach of funny narration in almost all of his major works of fiction. In his accounts, he ridicules the pompous, self-indulgent old world in mocking shades. He developed his work by sketching upon the views and sensations of his years as a child. He narrates about his boyhood ambitions to be the pilot of your riverboat. The episodic encounters of Huck and Jim present us with an illustration of the world in a social point of view by symbolically using the banking institutions of the river and the river that runs through them it to portray our activities in the world, in a realistic way. In *The Gilded Age*, he uses interpersonal satire to explore personality in an environment of speculation and unsteady beliefs, all in the name to getting wealthy, whether at the expense of others or not. Twain, who through the years had turned directly into a disillusioned pessimist, he cynically defined the people as a lost contemporary society, which acquired become obvious credited to individualism.

Mark also uses the aspects of vernacular in the realism movements. His use of colloquial words which can be real and express in effect, and use of simple word set ups makes his work very unique. He also uses grammatical wrong wording that is quality of the spoken language. He uses this colloquialism to powerfully cast his personas unique in their daily lives in a sensational way. The fact that his personas have different ethnic settings reveals that they speak in different ways probably with strong accents, which is the basic ideology of local colorism in his work. Like is the situation with Huck and Jim, who talk differently for their different cultural options. His use of humor is another element he uses to describe realism in his work. Most of his writings are comical and contain functional jokes. Most of his jokes and remarks are his exaggerated testimonies of his life activities. He not only uses this jokes to make people chuckle but also as a type of artistic approach of criticizing public injustices and mocking the romanticism genre.

In the publication *Huckleberry Finn*, Mark Twain uses the type Huck, a young lad who referred to as using the local dialect in arena development takes on the role

of narrator. The illustration of heroes and tale renditions are both comical and cleverly iconic. Huck is referred to as being illiterate and superstitious; however, he happens to have indigenous intelligence and concern-instinctive fads that help him reach the right decisions on certain important concerns. After running from his cruel dad, he complies with Jim, a runaway slave and alongside one another they start a long voyage down the Mississippi River on a boat. This describes how we are in times faced by life's obstacles and we choose to run away, rather than face them. Through the passage, Huck matches members of different areas, which helps him overcome his preceding narrow-mindedness and he learns to revere Jim. The book describes the several classes of people that Huck meets symbolically through the river finance institutions on their quest. The thread which operates through exploration after exploration is the aspect of human being cruelty to others.

The need for mark as an authentic article writer is the literary creativity he utilizes in his books. First of all, the language he uses to create his novels is simple and immediate colloquial speech. Second, the story and form of his writings provides his novels both a realistic and symbolic aspect. Thirdly, he describes the way the people is damned pursuing the sort of actions and decisions we make relating to various problems.

Although Make and Howells distributed the same understanding in explaining the realities of life in the American culture, all of them experienced a different stress. Howells preferred to bottom part his argument how the middle category people resided and conducted themselves in life. Twain concentrated his discussion on having folks from a certain region take the center-stage in his stories-local colorism, that was a unique style in the American fictitious realism. Local Colorism was an extraordinary way in the literary realism time. Generally, the writings by the neighborhood colorists were focused on the life span of some small, specific regions. This sort of books portrayed the individuals from a specific time, which can be manifested by its practices, language, attire and other peculiar customs that have

failed to come of age through social pressure. The writing is performed from a personal experience point of view, whereby they committed themselves to minutely and effectively describe just how of life in these areas. Through personal experience, they depicted a fantastic environment, which advised that the life span of the natives was greatly influenced by the conditions of the surroundings. The works of Symbol Twain and Hamlin Garland are characterized by this component of local colors of individuals. (Railton)

Henry Adam (1843-1916), was a well-known American-born British author and author of the realism motion. Among his highly attributable works of fiction are *The American* (1877), *The Family portrait of a Lady* (1881), *The Flip of the Screw* (1898), as well as the *Ambassadors* (1903). His works were generally intimate narrative with well toned characters which were set amongst revealing social observations on political affairs, social school and status. He greatly explored subject matter on feminism, personal flexibility and moral decency. In his novels and short reviews, he employs the inside monologue technique and method of ensure the viewers' pleasure of character way and sensitivity. Wayne often compares the lifestyle and perceptions of New World with the Old World.

In his writing, Henry Adam who greatly adored the early Western culture portrayed a poor image of the money-oriented and twisted life of the People in the usa. He became a English citizen through naturalization, arguing that he assumed that the People in the usa lacked a culture, a reason why he preferred the European civilization. In his major works more so the novels and essays made him a dominant shape in the American world of literature. You will discover three durations in his literary profession, in the first his main interest was at global subject issues. James's international theme is also another aspect that he uses in imaginary realism.

He uses America and European countries as the international environment, which centers around the issues between both of these very diverse cu1tures. Having diverse moral, People in the usa are naive, ignorant, unsophisticated and

individualistic in comparison with Western whose personality was that of cultural erosion, deceit and urbanity, a turmoil develops. The American searching for success in European countries would be easily deceived and betrayed by the civilized Europeans. In the same context he also uses love and marriage as central things of the issues between these two value structures. The type undergoes an agonizing development of religious nourishment and reaching an awareness of good and evil from this confrontation. He regards the conflicts between two diverse societies and the emotional and honest problems Americans in European countries and Europeans in America experienced.

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Henry James's natural elements are distinguished by his internal realism style that he uses to tackle the subject matter. His world of fiction is more worried about the inner aspects of life of an individual instead of the obvious real human serves. He makes specific perception and expression of every moment senses of personal experience to be the dramatic creation of puzzlement and great studies. We get to view individuals and activities as they are sorted out within an individual's

consciousness and entail ourselves in this experience. This stress on subconscious realism on the individual perception demonstrates this was a significant improvement in the writing of books and some sort of big affect on future years. James is commonly considered as the initiator of emotional realism, an idea which he incorporated in his work, whereby the character types are portrayed as using a stream of awareness.

In *Daisy Miller*, one of his own most well-known works, Henry James uses Frederick, an American emigrant as the narrator of the storyplot. While on a trip to Switzerland, Frederick fits the Millers. The Millers, who are American, believe in social flexibility and individuality unlike the Europeans. Daisy, little girl to Mrs. Miller does not regard the complex policies underlying carry out in European population. Daisy's adventurous behavior and insufficient concern from her mother leave Winterbourne surprised. She later dies of malaria. The theme of the book is an evaluation between America and Europe, centered on the conflict of these two cultures in regards to their different social worth, the moral decadence in Europe and its repercussion as defined through the loss of life of Daisy.

James's literary criticism, referred to as the theme of the *Fine Art of Fiction*. His imaginary criticism is an essential element of his insight to literature. It really is both apprehensive with outward manifestation and dedicated to personality ideals. This theme plainly implies that the program of the narrative is to provide life as it truly is. He depicts incident such as illusion, desolation, bonuses, agony and encouragement. His narrative standpoint and the language he uses are other themes or templates in his realistic literature. Through this literary skill, he places a mental health emphasis in the story. By causing his heroes build themselves in the story, devoid of authorial intrusion, we record the core storyline by reading it through the intellects of the protagonists and in that respect we reach show in their natural perspectives of life. For his dialect, James makes a careful selection of words that is supposed to draw out the clear and designed meaning without the ambiguity even

though it is not easy to comprehend his vocabulary. This made Henry Adam one of the most important realists of this time through his skilled design of writing.

The reports of F. Scott Fitzgerald (1896-1940) present the edgy and bold atmosphere of the 1920s, a disappointment that resulted from the battle. Fitzgerald's distinctive subject material is articulated expressively in his novel *THE FANTASTIC Gatsby*. He argues that there surely is a propensity of the ambitions that youths yearn for end in letdown and disillusionment. Fitzgerald uncovers that the failing of some main American moral expectations such as liberty, interpersonal harmony, promoting calmness and good governance are elements which were endangered by the demands of the 20th hundred years civilization.

Ernest Hemmingway, who was also another writer at that time (1899-1961) argued that fatality, violence on the globe War I and the bloodshed influenced him to conclude that conceptual verbal communication was typically vacant and therefore a misleading element. He left out over emphasized wordings from his works, to simple sentence structure. For some reason his writing was inspired by Mark Twain who influenced his style of writing. He dwelt on sensible things and activities. He stuck to an honest code that emphasized the substance of elegance under pressure, with his central people being quiet physically powerful who treated women inappropriately. His books include: *Sunlight Also Increases* and *A Farewell to Forearms*. He was one a copy writer who greatly detested this new civilization where the individuals were inelegant and their activities were very much individualistic.

Through her books, Toni Morrison (1930-1992) has used a number of themes and Practices which represent her contribution to realism in the American books arena. She uses the aspect of sense of damage to spell it out how she deeply feels for the Afro-Americans for loss they have observed in their motion from the rural regions of the south to the metropolitan centers in the north. They can be depicted as a people who have lost their sense of living as a modern culture, a disconnection

with their past and traditions. Their culture of dental tradition of tale narration and folktales was no longer a basis of their power as a people. Other foundations of these togetherness like music which they used as a recovering element, had been adsorbed by their integration into the white community. Hence portraying a culture that had completely lost touch using their roots and got sought to live in a more complex and genuine way, as opposed to their traditional way of life that entailed living as a centered community and getting a shared background. She also portrays her character types as folks who are in a regular struggle of hoping to identify with society and fulfill oneself. Thee elements of having societal root base, and a community to individuality with, which implies having a distributed history is exactly what these African-Americans have abandoned to look at the American culture. Anybody would you not belong to a community is generally regarded as lost, while those who still retain their practices and neighborhoods are depicted as having a high chance of surviving. The lack of societal roots and the detachment of an individual from the culture lead with their being alienated. Regarding to her, ancestors are also a necessary part of life for they give cultural information and a link to days gone by. They are likely to guide and become worried about our welfare like parents and grandparents.

In her novel, *The Bluest Eyeball*, ancestors is one of the distinctive uniqueness of the dark community literature, that they have actually abandoned for a far more sensible and fulfilling life. The aspect of characters in extreme situations is also another theme Toni Morrison uses in her books. She places her individuals in intense situations; she then makes them to the advantage beyond their items of endurance. These situations disclose their basic personality. Even the good people conclude acting in some very horrifying ways. Through this induced push, people are explained in their real manner rather than in their pretentious good home. Other themes in her works include responsibility, liberty and loss of innocence.

In conclusion, American Realism was a transformative literary and artistic movement that emerged in the late 19th century, reflecting the evolving American society during a period of significant change. It was characterized by its commitment to portraying everyday life with unvarnished honesty, focusing on ordinary people and their experiences. Writers like Mark Twain, Henry James, F. Scott Fitzgerald, Ernest Hemingway, and Toni Morrison played pivotal roles in shaping this movement, each offering their unique perspective on realism.

American Realism found its roots in the aftermath of the Civil War, a time when the United States underwent rapid industrialization, urbanization, and social change. This period of transformation provided a rich backdrop for authors to explore and depict the challenges of everyday life, social injustices, and the clash between traditional values and emerging modernity.

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